

Stereolithography Additive Manufacturing of Overmoded Spherical Filters

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Abstract—In this paper, we provide an overview of the stereolithography (SLA) manufacturing process applied to the design of microwave filters. For that purpose, a spherical cavity that operates with the higher order mode TE_{101} has been used in order to design filters oriented for additive manufacturing. The characteristics of such mode (high Q -factor and size) makes it an interesting choice for filters manufactured with 3-D printers. For validation purposes, two doublet prototypes with different configurations and mechanical structures have been manufactured with an SLA 3-D printer, metallized, and measured. Results show various discrepancies between the two prototypes: with measurements matching fairly well with the simulations for one prototype, while a certain frequency shift is present for the other one.

Index Terms—3-D printing, additive manufacturing (AM), bandpass filter, stereolithography (SLA), transmission zero (TZ).

I. INTRODUCTION

Generally, waveguide filters are the primary selection for systems with a high requirement of low insertion loss and high-power handling capabilities. In space communications, for instance, filters with low losses are an important requirement for transceiver in order to guarantee that the signal can be processed without losing information. Normally, waveguide filters are designed considering rectangular or circular waveguide cavities. Nevertheless, more recently, the use of spherical cavities to design filters has been reported [1]-[2]. The recent developments of additive manufacturing (AM) have made of spherical cavities an interesting choice to design filters since it provides lower losses than other classical waveguide cavities (rectangular and cylindrical). Typically, waveguide filters are designed to operate with the fundamental mode, as for the spherical cavity in [1]. However, higher order modes have also been applied for the design of filters in order to obtain more compact structures, or the possibility of introducing transmission zeros (TZs) and create selective filter responses. Nevertheless, the complexity of the designs increases as well as the difficulty to deal with unwanted excited spurious near the bandpass. In regards to spherical filters, in [2], the use of the mode TM_{211} working in Ka-band was used in order to obtain a higher unloaded quality factor (Q_u), as well as an increased volume of the filter in comparison to the filter operating with the fundamental mode. Moreover, in [2], slots

Fig. 1. Representation of the first three spherical modes.

Fig. 2. Representation of the different modes depending on the radius and frequency of the spherical cavity.

are used to interrupt certain surface currents and improve the spurious performance level. The theoretical improvement of the Q_u is about 15% working at 31 GHz.

More recently, the mode TE_{101} was introduced in [3]. The use of this resonators working with the mode TE_{101} is an interesting option to design filters with smaller losses than any other filter to be manufactured by using AM techniques. A doublet filter was fabricated in selective laser melting (SLM), showing a high Q -factor filter without plating. Correspondingly, in this work, a spherical cavity operating with the mode TE_{101} has been used to design two prototypes based on two different 2-pole filter designs. In this case, employing the technique known as stereolithography (SLA). The different steps followed to obtain the two prototypes are explained, and their responses are then compared to the simulations in order to prove the viability of this technology in terms of Q -factor, while providing mass reduction in comparison to components manufactured with classical fabrication techniques.

Fig. 3. S-parameters of doublet with a 90° rotation between input-output and middle aperture.

Fig. 4. S-parameters of doublet with a 135° rotation between input-output and middle aperture.

II. SPHERICAL MODES

The spherical modes can be identified by the indices n , m and l . For this paper, we are considering the mode TE_{101} ($n = 1$, $m = 0$, $l = 1$) for the design of the filter. A view of the E -field of the first three modes can be seen in Fig. 1, where the E -field has been represented only on two planes (ZY and XY). It should be noticed that the spherical cavity has a high number of degenerate modes, but in Fig. 1, the modes have been represented with the index $m = 0$. For the mode TE_{101} , the E -field is represented in the XY -plane, and as can be seen from Fig. 1, the E -field is mainly concentrated around the center of the cavity, forming a circular pattern around it. If we analyze its Q_u , the TE_{101} presents a theoretical value of 23000 at 10 GHz (in this case, using aluminum as material), whereas the Q_u of the fundamental mode is 10600 at the same frequency. But in order to resonate at the same frequency as the fundamental mode (TM_{101}), the radius must be increased about 1.61, as represented in Fig. 2. On the other hand, in order to resonate at the same frequency as the fundamental mode for the TM_{201} mode, the radius must be increased about 1.13,

Fig. 5. (a) 3-D cad view of the two part with a 40° printing orientation of the filter with supports. (b) Manufactured parts. (c) 3-D cad view of a part with a 0° printing orientation of the filter with supports.

but its theoretical Q_u is 12400 (using aluminum) at 10 GHz, which is almost half the Q_u of the spherical cavity operating with the TE_{101} mode. The increase of the radius in order to excite higher order modes, like in the case of TE_{101} , brings the advantage of improving the manufacturing tolerances at high frequencies, something quite challenging when manufacturing filters in AM.

In conclusion, the use of the TE_{101} mode implies bigger cavities, but this is an advantage from the tolerance point of view when higher frequencies are considered. Furthermore, there is the additional advantage of a higher Q_u .

III. FILTER DESIGN

A filter can be implemented by means of input-output E -plane apertures connected to the cavity. Regardless of the rotation angle around the z -axis (between input and output irises of the cavity), the mode TE_{101} is always excited. However, other modes can also be excited depending on the rotation angle, generating as a result a TZ. A coupling matrix could be implemented with source-to-load coupling, either positive or negative, depending on the selected rotation angle, but its analysis becomes rather difficult because of the interaction between the different spurious modes, which could be more or less excited for different rotations angles. An example of different selected rotations to design two-pole filters can be observed in Figs. 3 and 4. In the next section, two manufactured prototypes based on these two configurations are shown.

IV. EXPERIMENTAL RESULTS

One of the major concerns when it comes to the mechanical structure is the contact between manufactured pieces. As a result, in this work two approaches have been used in order to investigate different mechanical structures, evaluate how good their contact is, and see the differences between them

Fig. 6. Photos of the two prototypes: (a) Prototype 1 without supports. (b) Prototype 1 with silver painting. (c) Prototype 1 electroplated. (d) Prototype 2 without support. (e) Prototype 2 with silver painting. (f) Prototype 2 electroplated and assembled.

regarding their measured responses. The first prototype is a 90° filter configuration as the inset of Fig. 3, while the second prototype is a 135° filter configuration as the inset of Fig. 4. For both filters, two pieces cut through the E -plane were realized. However, considering that the operating mode is the TE_{101} , this cut won't have almost effect on their responses, since the currents generated by the mode in the cavity surface are orthogonal to the cut. Both filter were fabricated with a Formlabs Form 2 3-D printer.

The first approach consisted in designing a mechanical structure with a classical rectangular shape around the external part of the filter. An internal frame right next to the edges of the filter was added in order to increase the pressure towards the edges and guarantee a better contact. An external frame near the external edges of the filter has also been added in order to avoid deformations. The printing orientation of the component inserted in the corresponded software used for the 3-D printer was selected to be 40° as shown in Fig. 5(a). As can be seen, supports have been included to makes sure it adheres well to the base of the 3-D printer and avoids collisions. No supports were included in the internal part of the filter in order to provide a better finished surface. Fig. 5(b), also shows a photo of the manufactured parts before removing them from the 3-D printer.

The second approach that was followed, consisted in having a mechanical structure with a circular shape around the filter with an equal distance of the supporting screws between the internal and external frames. The printing orientation of manufacturing was selected to be 0° as shown in Fig. 5(b), and similarly to the first approach, no internal supports were included. A printing orientation of 0° allows for a faster printing process but the number of elements that can be included in the platform are more limited. The z -axis resolution for both approaches was selected to the minimum accepted for the 3-D printer, in this case of 0.025 mm. No post-processing like ultraviolet (UV) light curing was applied. Since the technique SLA produces plastic components, this imposes a big draw-

back as no conductivity is present around the inner surfaces. As a result, metallization of the surface is necessary. The most common way is to use electroplating techniques (e.g., [4]), but other techniques like electroless plating have also been considered to metallized microwave components fabricated in plastic (e.g., [5]). Nevertheless, when using the electroplating technique, it is almost required to split the components so the inner parts can be easily accessible for an easier metallization. Electroplating works on conducting surfaces, and plastic is an insulator. For this reason, before the electroplating, the internal surface of the filter were painted by using conductive silver paint. In this work, the electroplating technique was employed, which consisted in a circuit composed of a copper anode connected to the positive of a voltage generator, a component (the filter to be metallized) connected to the negative of the voltage generator, and a copper solution that was used as the medium. In this case, a small container was used, a separation of about 6 cm between cathode and anode was established. The current for the electroplating has been set to 0.2 A. In this work, the electroplating process was used for about 30 min for each individual part. Photos of the different filters after the manufacturing are shown in Fig. 6 for different phases of the process: after cleaning the residuals of resin found on the parts, after adding a layer of silver painting, and after applying the electroplating technique. No tuning screws were used, mainly due to the complexity of introducing external elements inside the cavity that could alter the E -field, which is concentrated in the center of the cavity. A comparison between the ideal response with the measured response for the first approach is shown in Fig. 7. As can be seen, there is no TZ. It has been observed that the contact was not perfect, with small gaps in certain areas and having more pressure towards the external frames than the internal ones. Nevertheless, similar to [3], the filter response has a frequency shift, in this case of about 70 MHz. The return loss at the center frequency is better than 20 dB.

On the other hand, for the second approach, the ideal

Fig. 7. Measured and simulated responses of prototype 1.

Fig. 8. Measured and simulated responses of prototype 2.

Fig. 9. Close-up view of the measured responses (red lines) compared to the simulated responses with similar losses (black lines). (a) Prototype 1 with FBW of 1.2%. (b) Prototype 2 with FBW of 1%.

response and the measured response are depicted in Fig. 8, and it is observed that both responses match perfectly well with a small frequency deviation on the midband response as well as the upper TZ of about 5 MHz. The return loss is better than 20 dB throughout the passband. In this case, the contact between the different parts was well realized. Moreover, Fig. 9 shows a close-up of the insertion loss for both

prototypes. Prototype 1 presents better insertion losses than prototype 2, nevertheless, it has a slightly higher fractional bandwidth (FBW), so smaller insertion losses were expected for prototype 2. The extracted measured Q_u was 1200 for both of them. From the comparison of both responses, several conclusions can be extracted: the contact between both pieces is important as to guarantee a good response over the whole frequency span; the printing orientation could have affected the dimensions of the cavity, deforming the cavity and changing its resonant frequency towards lower frequencies; moreover, the quality of the metallization affects the Q_u of the filters, with a simple layer of silver, followed by 30 min of electroplating, the measured Q_u was of 1200, which is actually low for this particular mode. This aspect needs to be studied thoroughly in order to guarantee a better metallization.

V. CONCLUSIONS

Two filters based on spherical cavities operating with the mode TE_{101} have been presented in this paper. This mode provides a higher Q_u than its counterpart modes, as well as a better scalability factor to higher frequencies due to its larger radius. Additionally, the round shape of the spherical cavity makes this geometry not very easy to be manufactured by using traditional manufacturing technique, On the other hand, this geometry is particularly suitable when AM is used. In this paper, two prototypes with different configurations were designed, manufactured with a SLA 3-D printer, and measured. Results showed some differences between measurements and simulations over the frequency band, with a big frequency shift for one of the prototypes. Finally, the Q_u obtained in the two prototypes is less than expected, nevertheless, this aspect of Q_u will be studied in more detailed.

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